

Bacteriological Analysis of Suya Sold in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

Okoye Chinenye Vivian¹, Ohiakwu Joachim Ezeadila², Agubuokwu Valentine Chukwuka³, Nneka Adinife Obidinma⁴, Umezina Loretta Chinenye⁵ & Osilade Adewole⁶

¹Department of Applied Microbiology and Brewing, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Anambra State, Nigeria

²Department of Applied Microbiology and Brewing, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Anambra State, Nigeria

³Department of Environmental Health sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Anambra State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Applied Microbiology and Brewing, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

⁵Department of Public Health, Spiritan University, Nneochi, Abia State, Nigeria

⁶Department of Health Systems Management, School of Public Health, University of Portharcourt, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: Okoye Chinenye Vivian, Email: cv.okoye@unizik.edu.ng

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 4TH Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Bacteriological Analysis Suya Awka Nigeria</p>	<p>Five (5) suya samples were collected from different suya vendors at Awka, Anambra State. The bacteriological analysis of the samples were carried out using standard methods. Bacteria that were isolated include <i>Proteus mirabilis</i> (8.49%), <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (5.57%), <i>Bacillus cereus</i> (10.07%), <i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> (7.69%), <i>Proteus vulgaris</i> (11.67%), <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> (12.47%), <i>Salmonella typhi</i> (14.06%) and <i>Escherichia coli</i> (0.79%), <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (13.79%) and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (15.38%). It was observed that the suya sample 4 collected from a suya vendor at Aroma junction gave the highest bacterial count of 10.7x10⁴ while the suya sample 3 collected from a suya vendor at Ifite gave the lowest bacterial count of 3.8x10⁵. Following the outcome of the findings from the research, it has being vividly proven that suya sold in Awka are highly contaminated with different bacteria. Evidently, some of the organisms isolated from the samples are human pathogens as well as commensals or opportunistic pathogens with great tendency of causing infection to the body especially in immune-compromised individuals. The contaminations could have being caused by the use of contaminated tools, improper cooking as well as poor sanitary conditions in the course of its preparation and selling.</p>

1. Introduction

Suya, also known as Tsire, is a traditional Hausa (Nigerian) smoke-grilled spiced meat on skewer. Suya is generally made with thin-sliced spiced beef, lamb, goat, ram, or chicken arranged on wooden skewers (wikipedia.org/wiki/Suya). Suya is most popular as evening street food or snack, restaurant appetizer, and as accompaniment with drinks at bars and night spots.

Suya meat is thinly sliced and then marinated in a traditional Hausa spice mix called 'Yaji' which consists of dry hot chili & cayenne peppers, ginger, dried onion, ground peanut cake ('Kuli-Kuli'), salt and other spices. The skewered meats are doused with vegetable oil before they are cooked on the grill. The cooked Suya is usually sliced off the skewers and cut into bite-size bits. It is often served with an extra topping or side helping of 'Yaji' pepper mix as well as sliced onions and tomatoes, which may be requested grilled or raw as preferred (wikipedia.org/wiki/Suya). Although Suya is a traditional Hausa Nigerian dish, it has permeated the Nigerian society, being affordable for all and available everywhere. It has been called a unifying factor in Nigeria (Gambrell, 2012). Suya has become a Nigerian national dish, with different regions claiming the superiority of their recipe and methods of preparation, but similar grilled meat recipes are common in many West African countries (wikipedia.org/wiki/Suya). Today Suya meat has gained wide popularity and it is being consumed by majority. Most of the processors of this meat were found in strategic locations and were people who does not have much formal education and as a result still uses traditional methods of handling, processing, exposing it after preparation and packaging the products, which are considered to be unhygienic, unsafe and can result in rapid deterioration of the processed meat if not consumed within a short period of time. The processors have been accustomed to collecting old newspapers from different homes and using same to package Suya meat for their customers, which are considered to be dirty and dusty (Marsh *et al.*, 2007). It is in view of the aforementioned observations that this study was conducted to investigate the bacteriological quality of suya sold in Awka, Anambra State.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Samples Collection

The samples were collected as stated by Cheesbrough (2006). Five samples of suya were obtained randomly from popular suya vendors in Awka. The spots were located at Temporary site, Aroma, Nkwoamaenyi, Eke-Awka and Ifite-Awka.

The samples were immediately wrapped in a sterile aluminium foil to prevent contamination and then transported to the microbiology laboratory of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State for bacteriological analysis within two hours of collection.

2.2 Samples Pre-treatment

Each of the samples was enriched in sterile nutrient broth and incubated at 27°C for twenty-four hours. A tenfold serial dilution of each of the enriched samples was then carried out.

2.3 Determination of the total bacteria count

One milliliter aliquot of the serially dilutions 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} each was pipette and plated on nutrient agar supplemented with 1µg/ml of ketoconazole using the pour plate method. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. Developed colonies were counted to obtain the total bacteria count using the formular:

$$\text{Total bacteria count} = \frac{N}{DXV}$$

Discrete colonies were purified by sub-culturing them into nutrient agar. Pure cultures were stored by inoculating them onto nutrient agar slants supplemented with 1µg/ml of ketoconazole and were subsequently identified using standard methods.

2.4 Characterization and Identification of the Isolates

The isolates were characterized and identified based on their cultural characteristics and biochemical reactions obtained. Tests that were used for the identification include Gram reaction, motility test, catalase test, coagulase test, oxidase test, urease test, citrate test, indole test, methyl red test and carbohydrate fermentation test (Cheesbrough, 2006).

2.5 Gram Reaction

This was carried out to differentiate gram-positive from gram-negative bacteria. A smear from a 24 hour culture was prepared on a grease-free slide. The smear was air-dried and fixed by gently passing it over a bunsen flame. The smear was flooded with crystal violet and allowed to stand for 1 minute. The stain was rinsed with running water. It was flooded with lugol's iodine solution and allowed to stand for one minute and rinsed with running water. This was followed by decolourization with alcohol for ten seconds. The slide was washed with water. It was then counter - stained with safranin for thirty seconds, washed with water, air-dried and examined under the oil immersion lens (X100) of the microscope.

2.6 Motility Test

This test was aimed at identifying motile bacteria. A semi-solid agar medium was prepared in a test tube and a colony of the test organism was inoculated by a single stab made down the center of the tube using a straight wire. This tube was incubated at 37°C and examined at intervals by holding it up to the light and the stab line looked at to determine motility. Non-motile isolates produced growths that were confined to the stabline, having sharply defined margins and leaving the surrounding medium clearly transparent while motile bacteria diffused and produced hazy growths that spread throughout the medium making it to be slightly opaque.

2.7 Catalase Test

This was to differentiate those bacteria that produce catalase. A drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide was made on a clean and grease free slide. A wire loopful of the test isolate was mixed with the hydrogen peroxide on the slide. The production of gas bubbles from the mixture which occurred almost immediately was an indication of a positive reaction while absence of gas bubbles was a negative reaction.

2.8 Coagulase Test

This was used to identify bacteria that produce coagulase which cause the plasma to clot by converting fibrinogen in the plasma to fibrin. A drop of physiological saline was placed on each end of a slide. With the aid of a wire loop, a colony of the test isolate was picked using the wire loop and emulsified in each drop to make two thick suspensions. A drop of human plasma was added to one of the suspensions and mixed gently. The clumping of the mixture within 10 seconds was a positive reaction. No plasma was added to the second suspension and this served as the control so as to differentiate any granular appearance of the organism from true coagulase clumping.

2.9 Oxidase Test

The test was carried out using the method described by Cheesbrough. A filter paper was moistened with the substrate (1% tetramethyl-p- phenylenediamine dihydrochloride) and a colony of the isolate was picked using a wire loop and mixed with the reagent on the filter paper. Positive result was indicated by the development of dark purple color (indophenols) within 10 seconds while negative result was indicated by the absence of color.

2.10 Urease Test

This test was aimed at identifying bacteria that produce urease enzyme which hydrolyzes urea to give ammonia and carbon (iv) oxide. The test organism was heavily inoculated into Christensen's urea broth in bijou bottles using a sterile wire loop and phenol red was used as an indicator. These organisms in the bijou bottles were incubated for 24hrs at 37°C. A pink colour in the medium showed a positive result.

2.11 Citrate Test

This test was to identify bacteria that can use citrate as its source of carbon. Simmon's citrate medium was inoculated with a loopful of peptone water culture of the pure isolate and incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs. A colour change from green to blue after the 48 hrs incubation was an indication of a positive result while the absence of any colour change was an indication of a negative result.

2.12 Indole Test

This was carried out to test for indole production by the test organism. A loopful of twenty-four hour pure culture of the isolate was inoculated into a sterilized test tube containing four milliliters (4 ml) of tryptophan broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After the 24 hours, 0.5 ml of Kovac's reagent was added. The production of a red ring on the surface layer within 10 minutes was an indication of a positive reaction.

2.13 Voges Proskauer Test

A loopful of the test organism was inoculated into a test tube containing glucose phosphate peptone water and incubated at 35°C for 5 days. 0.6 ml of 50% alcoholic naphthol and 0.2 ml of 40% potassium hydroxide was added into the inoculated medium. The mixture was shaken and left to stand. A red colour was an indication of a positive result while the development of a yellow colour was an indication of a negative result.

2.14 Sugar Fermentation Test

This test was used to determine the ability of isolates to utilize some selected sugars such as mannitol, glucose, lactose and sucrose. Peptone water each containing 1% of the following sugars, mannitol, glucose, lactose and sucrose and a bromothymol blue indicator, Durham tubes was prepared, sterilized and thereafter inoculated with the test organisms and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Development of gas in the Durham tubes and a change in the colour of the indicator in the peptone water from blue to yellow was an indication of a positive reaction. A control was set up without the organism inoculated.

3. Results

A total of 377 cfu units of bacteria were isolated from the 5 suya samples. These include *Proteus mirabilis*, 32 (8.49%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 21 (5.57%), *Bacillus cereus* 38 (10.07%), *Bacillus licheniformis*, 29 (7.69%), *Proteus vulgaris*, 44 (11.67%), *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, 47 (12.47%), *Salmonella typhi*, 53 (14.06%), *Escherichia coli*, 3 (0.79%), *Bacillus subtilis*, 52 (13.79%) and *Staphylococcus aureus*, 58 (15.40%).

3.1 Morphological Characteristics of the Isolates

As shown in table 1, isolates S₁ and S₅ were swamy, transparent and wavy colonies and were also gram-negative rods. S₂ gave a smooth round colonies with green colour gram negative rods. S₃ were irregular colonies that were grayish white and gram positive rods. Colonies of S₄ were white in colour and also gram positive rods. S₅ were swamy growth, transparent and wavy colonies that were gram negative rods. S₆ and S₁₀ were yellow colonies that were gram positive cocci in chains. S₉ were white large and irregular edged colonies that were gram positive rods in chains. S₇ was smooth pale and slimy positive rods. S₈ were gram negative rods.

Table 1: Gram reaction and morphological characteristics of the isolates after growth on nutrient agar at 37°C

Isolates	Colony morphology	Gram stain
S ₁	Swamy, transparent and wavy colonies	Gram-negative rods
S ₂	Smooth round and green colonies	Gram-negative rods
S ₃	Irregular colonies that are grayish white	Gram-positive rods
S ₄	Colonies are white in colour	Gram-positive rods
S ₅	Swamy, transparent and wavy colonies	Gram-negative rods
S ₆	Light yellow colonies	Gram-positive cocci in chains
S ₇	Smooth pale and slimy colonies	Gram-positive rods
S ₈	Smooth milky circular colonies	Gram-negative rods
S ₉	White, large and irregular edged colonies	Gram-positive rods in chains
S ₁₀	pale yellow colonies	Gram-positive cocci in chains

3.2 Biochemical Test Reactions

As shown in table 2, isolates S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄, S₆, S₉ and S₁₀ were catalase positive while isolates S₅ and S₇ were catalase negative. Isolates S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄, S₅, S₇ and S₈ were coagulase negative where as S₆, S₉ and S₁₀ were coagulase positive. Furthermore isolates S₁, S₅, S₆ and S₉ were oxidase negative but other isolates were positive. S₄, S₆, S₈ and S₁₀ were motile other isolates were non

motile. S₁, S₅, S₉ and S₁₀ gave positive reaction to urease test while other isolates were negative. Isolates S₁, S₃, S₅, S₈ and S₁₀ were citrate negative while other isolates were positive. All the isolates were Voges proskauer negative except isolates S₃ and S₄ that were positive.

Table 2: Biochemical Test Reactions of the Isolates

Biochemical test	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀
Cat	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
Coa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
Ox	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+
Mo	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
Ur	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+
Ind	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
Cit	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	-
Vp	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Org	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

Key

Cat-Catalase Test

Coa- Coagulase Test

Ox-Oxidase Test

Mo-Motility Test

Ur-Urease Test

Ind-Indole Test

Cit-Citrate Test

VP- Voges proskauer test

Org-organism

+Positive

--Negative

3.3 Sugar fermentation test of the isolates

As shown in table 3, isolates S₁S₂S₅S₆S₇ and S₉ were able to ferment glucose with only isolate S₁ and S₅ producing acid and gas while other isolates were not glucose fermenting. Isolates S₁, S₂, S₅, S₆, S₇ and S₉ were able to ferment sucrose while S₃, S₄, S₈ and S₁₀ were not sucrose fermenting. Isolates S₁, S₄, S₅, S₆, S₇ and S₉ were able to ferment lactose with only S₄ able to produce acid and gas while S₂, S₃, S₈ and S₁₀ were not lactose fermenting. Isolates S₁, S₂, S₄, S₅, S₆ and S₇ were mannitol fermenting with isolates S₅ and S₇ able to produce acid and gas while S₃, S₈, S₉ and S₁₀ were not mannitol fermenting.

Table 3: Results of Sugar Fermentation Test of the Isolates

Sugars	Isolates									
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀
GLu	AG	+	-	-	AG	+	+	-	+	-
Su	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-
Lac	+	-	-	AG	AG	+	+	-	+	-
Man	+	+	-	+	AG	+	AG	-	-	-

KEY

Glu-glucose

Su-sucrose

Lac-lactose

Man-mannitol

AG-acid and gas

+positive

--Negative

3.4 Total Aerobic Plate Count

As shown in table 4, sample 4 has the highest aerobic plate count (5.4×10^5 and 10.7×10^4) while sample 3 gave the lowest aerobic plate count (5.9×10^4 and 3.8×10^5). Isolates S₁₀ gave the highest frequency (15.38%) while isolate S₉ gave the lowest frequency (0.79%) as shown in table 5.

Table 4: Total Aerobic Plate Count

sample	Viable count (cfu/ml)				
	Plate 1(10 ⁻⁴)	Plate 2 (10 ⁻⁵)	mean	Plate 1	Plate 2
1	62	51	56.5	6.2x10 ⁴	5.1x10 ⁵
2	78	43	60.5	7.8x10 ⁴	4.3x10 ⁵
3	59	38	48.5	5.9x10 ⁴	3.8x10 ⁵
4	107	54	80.5	10.7x10 ⁴	5.4x10 ⁵
5	71	49	60	7.1x10 ⁴	4.9x10 ⁵

Table 5: Isolation Frequency of Bacteria from the Suya Samples

Isolates	Bacteria	Number isolated (cfu)	Frequency (%)
S ₁	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	32	8.49
S ₂	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	21	5.57
S ₃	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	38	10.07
S ₄	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	29	7.69
S ₅	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	44	11.67
S ₆	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	47	12.47
S ₇	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	53	14.06
S ₈	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	0.79
S ₉	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	52	13.79
S ₁₀	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	58	15.40

4. Discussion

Meat contains all the nutrients necessary for microbial growth and this makes it to be susceptible to microbial contamination (Adam, 1999). Suya been a meat product has been shown to be contaminated by so many organisms of which some of them are pathogenic while some are non pathogenic. The possible sources of suya contamination include use of meat of unhealthy animals, washing of meat with contaminated water, contamination by flies and use of contaminated equipment such as knife and other utensils, germinating spore from improperly cooked meat, handlers as well as unclean wraps (Jill, 1991).

In the present day study, the bacteria isolated were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus licheniformis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Escherichia coli*. The result of this study correlated with the findings of previous research on meat and meat products such as that of Chukwura and Muojekwu (2002) which stated that microbiological analysis of meat samples in Awka Urban of Anambra State, indicated contamination of meat samples by bacterial species such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and some enteric bacteria.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa isolated is commonly found in soil, water and decaying matter. It is an opportunistic human pathogen, mostly affecting immuno-compromised patients (Nester, 2001). Infection can affect many different parts of the body but infections typically target the respiratory tract causing bacterial pneumonia.

Christopher *et al.*, (2023) reported that *B. cereus* is a recognized food pathogen, and other species, particularly those of the *B. subtilis* group (*B. subtilis*, *B. licheniformis*, and *B. pumilus*), have been implicated in foodborne illnesses (shelef, 2003). Spores and vegetative forms of *B. cereus* are frequent inhabitants of soils, sediments, dust, natural water sources, vegetation, and many foods such as grains, dairy products, dried foods, spices, meats, and vegetables. *Bacillus licheniformis* is commonly found in the soil while *B. subtilis* is mainly found in soil and plant roots, but it also inhabits aquatic environments and the gastrointestinal tract of animals, including humans.

Of significance to humans are various strains of the species *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and were also isolated from the suya samples. While *S. epidermidis* is a mild pathogen, opportunistic only in people with lowered resistance, strains of *S. aureus* are major agents of wound infections, boils and other human skin infections and are one of the most common causes of food poisoning (www.britannica.com/science/Staphylococcus). *Staphylococcus aureus* has been incriminated in outbreaks especially with convenience type foods and foods that have been being prepared well in advance of service and kept at an ambient temperature for the microorganism (www.wikipedia.org/foodborne_diseases/staphyococcus). *Staphylococcus epidermidis*

Proteus species such as *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris* are commonly found in the soil, sewage, and manure. Although they are normal inhabitants of the colon and perineum but their numbers can be increased in individuals receiving antibiotic therapy. *Proteus mirabilis* is a human pathogen. It is an aerobic organism and belongs to the family enterobacteriaceae. Since *Proteus mirabilis* is a part of normal flora of human gastrointestinal tract so its presence in food suggests faecal contamination of the food (Talaro, 2002). *Proteus mirabilis* can cause food borne disease when contaminated foods are consumed (www.metapathogen.com).

Salmonella typhi is non spore forming, facultative anaerobic organism. It lives in the intestinal tract of warm and cold blooded animals and as a result is associated with faeces. In humans, it causes a disease known as salmonellosis resulting from a food borne infection or intoxication (www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/salmonella).

Escherichia coli is a normal commensal of the vertebrate large intestine so their presence in food or water suggests fecal contamination (Adams *et al.*, 1999). It causes traveller's diarrhea (involves adults on transit) and infantile diarrhea (which affects infants especially in the age of 0-2 years) (www.wikipedia.org/wiki/foodborne_illness).

5. Recommendation

Based on the results of this research, the following recommendations were made:

- There should be education of suya vendors on the need of observing personal hygiene during the preparation of suya so that food infection as a result of consumption of contaminated suya will be reduced.
- Meat of infected animals or sick animals should not be used for suya making so that these disease causing organisms will not be transmitted to humans.
- Meat for suya should be cut in small pieces and heated properly making sure that the internal temperature is at least up to 68°C in order to kill microbial spores that may be in the meat.
- Ingredients and utensils for preparing suya should be well washed before and after usage. Prepared suya should be well covered to prevent contamination by flies and should be served hot.
- Suya meats are to be stored between 50°C to 60°C to prevent the growth of microbes.

6. Conclusion

Following the outcome of the findings from this research, it is vividly proved that suya sold in Awka are highly contaminated with different bacteria. Evidently, some of the organisms isolated are human pathogens as well as commensals or opportunistic pathogens with great tendency of causing infection to the body especially in immune-compromised individuals. The contaminations resulted from unhealthy practices associated with its preparation and processing such as use of contaminated tools, improper cooking as well as poor sanitary conditions in the course of its preparation and selling. Conclusively, contamination of suya consist in using contaminated meat, improper cooking and unhealthy delivery of suya.

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